

Reports of the Finnish Environment Institute 7 | 2026

Interlaboratory comparison 12/2025

Analyses of biowaste compost quality parameters

Elli Auvinen, Liisa Maunuksela, Mirja Leivuori, Aija Pelkonen,
Mikko Lehtonen, Riitta Koivikko, and Markku Ilmakunnas

Suomen ympäristökeskus
Finlands miljöcentral
Finnish Environment Institute

Reports of the Finnish Environment Institute 7 | 2026

Interlaboratory comparison 12/2025

Analyses of biowaste compost quality parameters

Elli Auvinen, Liisa Maunuksela, Mirja Leivuori, Aija Pelkonen,
Mikko Lehtonen, Riitta Koivikko, and Markku Ilmakunnas

Suomen ympäristökeskus
Finlands miljöcentral
Finnish Environment Institute

Reports of the Finnish Environment Institute 7 | 2026

Finnish Environment Institute
Research Infrastructure

Author(s): Elli Auvinen¹⁾, Liisa Manuksela¹⁾, Mirja Leivuori²⁾, Aija Pelkonen¹⁾, Mikko Lehtonen¹⁾
Riitta Koivikko²⁾, and Markku Ilmakunnas²⁾

1) Finnish Food Authority

2) Finnish Environment Institute

Publisher and financier of publication: Finnish Environment Institute (Syke)
Latokartanonkaari 11, 00790 Helsinki, Finland Phone +358 295 251 000, syke.fi

Layout: Finnish Environment Institute

Cover photograph: Adobe Stock

The publication is available in the internet: syke.fi/publications | helda.helsinki.fi/syke.

ISBN 978-952-11-5831-5 (PDF)

ISSN 1796-1726 (online)

Year of issue: 2026

Abstract

Interlaboratory comparison 12/2025: Analyses of biowaste compost quality parameters

Finnish Food Authority, in collaboration with Proftest Syke's proficiency testing services, organized an interlaboratory comparison (ILC) in October-November 2025 for the analysis of quality parameters in biowaste compost. In total, 14 laboratories participated in the ILC. Either the robust mean, the mean or the median of the reported results was used as the assigned values for the measurands. The overall performance of the participants was evaluated using z scores. In this ILC, 93 % of the results were satisfactory when total deviation of 0.3 pH units for pH values and 6–20 % for the other measurands was accepted from the assigned value. Warm thanks to all participants of this ILC!

Keywords: biowaste compost, soil improver, pH, dry matter, bulk density, electrical conductivity, impurities, total nitrogen, organic matter, total organic carbon, stability, interlaboratory comparison

Tiivistelmä

Vertailumittaus 12/2025: Biojätekompostin laatuparametrien analyysit

Ruokavirasto järjesti yhteistyössä Proftest Syke vertailumittaustoiminnan kanssa loka-marraskuussa 2025 vertailumittauksen biojätekompostin laatuparametrien analyysille. Vertailumittaukseen osallistui yhteensä 14 laboratoriota. Testisuureiden vertailuarvoina käytettiin osallistujien tulosten robustia keskiarvoa, keskiarvoa tai mediaania. Osallistujien pätevyyden arviointi tehtiin z-arvojen avulla. Koko tulosaineistossa oli z-arvoilla arvioituna 93 % hyväksyttäviä tuloksia, kun vertailuarvosta sallittiin pH-määrityksissä 0,3 pH-yksikön ja muissa määrityksissä 6–20 %:n poikkeama. Kiitos pätevyyskokeen osallistujille!

Asiasanat: biojätekomposti, maanparannusaine, pH, kuiva-aine, tilavuuspaino, sähkönjohtavuus, epäpuhtaudet, kokonaistyyppi, orgaaninen aines, orgaaninen hiili, stabiilisuus, vertailumittaus

Sammandrag

Jämförelse mellan laboratorier 12/2025: Analyser av kvalitetsparametrar för bioavfallskompost

Livsmedelsverket genomförde tillsammans med Proftest Syke under november-december 2025 en jämförelse mellan laboratorier för organisationer som gör analyser av kvalitetsparametrar för bioavfallskompost. Totalt 14 deltagare tog del i testen. Som referensvärde av analytens koncentration användes robust medelvärde, medelvärde eller median av deltagarnas resultat. Resultaten värderades med hjälp av z-värden. I denna kompetensprövning var 93 % av resultaten acceptabla. Resultatet var acceptabelt, om det devierade mindre än 0,3 pH-enhet eller 6–20 % från referensvärdet. Ett varmt tack till alla deltagarna i testet!

Nyckelord: biokompost, pH, torrsubstans, bulkdensitet, elektrisk ledningsförmåga, föroreningar, totalt kväve, organiskt material, stabilitet, jämförelse

Contents

1 Introduction	9
2 Organising the interlaboratory comparison	10
2.1 Responsibilities.....	10
2.2 Participants.....	10
2.3 Samples and timetable.....	11
2.4 Homogeneity studies	11
2.5 Feedback from the interlaboratory comparison.....	12
2.6 Processing the data	12
2.6.1 Pretesting the data.....	12
2.6.2 Assigned values	12
2.6.3 Proficiency assessment procedure	13
3 Results and conclusions	14
3.1 Results	14
3.2 Analytical methods.....	16
3.2.1 Bulk density.....	16
3.2.2 Conductivity 25	16
3.2.3 Dry matter, DM	16
3.2.4 Impurities	17
3.2.5 Total nitrogen, N _{tot}	17
3.2.6 Organic matter	17
3.2.7 pH	17
3.2.8 Stability.....	18
3.2.9 Total organic carbon, TOC.....	18
3.3 Uncertainties of the reported results	18
4 Evaluation of the results	20
5 Summary	21
6 Summary in Finnish	22
References	23
Appendix 1. Participants in the interlaboratory comparison.....	24
Appendix 2. Sample preparation	25
Appendix 3. Homogeneity of the samples	26
Appendix 4. Feedback from the interlaboratory comparison.....	28
Appendix 5. Assigned values and their uncertainties	30
Appendix 6. Terms in the results tables	31
Appendix 7. Results of each participant	32
Appendix 8. Results of participants and their uncertainties	39
Appendix 9. Summary of the z scores	48

Appendix 10. z scores in ascending order	49
Appendix 11. Answers to the background survey on analytical methods	54
Appendix 12. Results grouped according to the methods	63
Appendix 13. Examples of measurement uncertainties reported by the participants	72

1 Introduction

Finnish Food Authority, in collaboration with ProfTest Syke's proficiency testing services, organised an interlaboratory comparison (ILC) in October-November 2025 (B2B 12/2025) for the analysis of quality parameters in biowaste compost. The following measurands were tested from two biowaste compost samples: pH, dry matter (DM), bulk density, electrical conductivity, impurities (IMP), total nitrogen (N_{tot}), organic matter, total organic carbon (TOC), and stability (oxygen uptake rate, OUR). This ILC is part of EU co-funded Bin2Bean project (bin2bean.eu).

Finnish Environment Institute (Syke) is the appointed National Reference Laboratory in the environmental sector in Finland. The duties of the reference laboratory include providing interlaboratory proficiency tests and other comparisons for analytical laboratories and other producers of environmental information. This interlaboratory comparison provides an external quality evaluation between laboratory results, and mutual comparability of analytical reliability. The interlaboratory comparison was carried out in accordance with the international standard ISO/IEC 17043 [1] and applying ISO 13528 [2] and IUPAC Technical report [3]. This interlaboratory comparison is not included in the ProfTest Syke accreditation scope (PT01, finas.fi/sites/en), however, its organisation follows the principles of accredited operations.

2 Organising the interlaboratory comparison

2.1 Responsibilities

Organiser and expert laboratory

Finnish Food Authority, Mustialankatu 3, FI-00790 Helsinki

Email: firstname.lastname@foodauthority.fi

Responsible organiser

Liisa Maunuksela

Elli Auvinen

Analytical experts

Mikko Lehtonen (stability, impurities)

Aija Pelkonen (the other measurands)

Expert laboratory Finnish Food Authority, Helsinki (T014, finas.fi/sites/en, measurements for impurities, N_{tot} , TOC, and stability are not included in the accredited scope)

Expert in interlaboratory comparison activities

ProfTest Syke, Finnish Environment Institute Syke, Mustialankatu 3, FI-00790 Helsinki, Finland,

Specialist for ILC activities

Mirja Leivuori

Substitute for the specialist

Riitta Koivikko

Email: firstname.lastname@syke.fi

ProfTest Syke technical assistance

Markku Ilmakunnas and Keijo Tervonen

Email: profTest@syke.fi

2.2 Participants

A total of 14 laboratories participated in this ILC (Appendix 1), seven from Finland and seven from abroad. Five participants reported that they have an accredited quality management system based on ISO/IEC 17025, while the rest of the participants did not report their accreditation status. From one laboratory, two different units participated. Ten participants used accredited analytical methods for at least some of the measurements. For this ILC, the expert laboratory has codes 4 and 15 in the result tables.

2.3 Samples and timetable

The sample matrices in this ILC consisted of biowaste composts of two different batches. Laboratories received both fresh and dried samples. Fresh samples were labeled as BioCom1 and BioCom2, while the corresponding dried samples were referred to as BioCom1_DG and BioCom2_DG. Samples for impurity analysis were labeled BioCom1_IMP and BioCom2_IMP. The following measurands were tested from the biowaste compost samples: pH, dry matter (DM), bulk density, electrical conductivity, impurities (IMP), total nitrogen (N_{tot}), organic matter, total organic carbon (TOC), and stability (oxygen uptake rate, OUR).

The two different compost samples were collected from a composting facility in Southern Finland. The sampling procedure was adapted from the principles of SFS-EN 12579 [4]. Each sample consisted of approximately 150 l of material collected from fifteen sampling points. The material was thoroughly mixed and transported to the Finnish Food Authority laboratory. The samples were pretreated following the main procedures of SFS-EN 13040 [5], including homogenising and sieving (<10 mm) [5]. The samples were then portioned into batches for participants. A subset was dried at 40 °C, sieved (<2 mm), and ground. All prepared samples were packed with cooling elements and shipped to the participating laboratories. The sample preparation is described in more detail in Appendix 2.

The samples were delivered to the participants on 27 October 2025. Based on the reported information, most of the participants received the samples on 29 October 2025.

The samples were requested to be measured as follows:

pH and electrical conductivity	at the latest by 7 November 2025
Other measurands	at the latest by 14 November 2025

The results were requested to be reported at the latest by 17 November 2025, and participants delivered them accordingly. The preliminary results report was delivered to the participants via ProfTestWEB on 1 December 2025.

2.4 Homogeneity studies

The homogeneity was tested for selected measurands from biowaste compost samples during the test period of the ILC by Finnish Food Authority. More detailed information on homogeneity testing is shown in Appendix 3. According to the homogeneity test results, the samples were considered sufficiently homogeneous for the purposes of the ILC. However, with respect to impurities, the sample was found to be non-homogeneous.

The measurement schedule for the round was intentionally kept short based on prior knowledge and therefore, no separate stability testing of the samples was performed.

2.5 Feedback from the interlaboratory comparison

The feedback from the interlaboratory comparison is shown in Appendix 4. The comments from the participants mainly dealt with reporting of the results, suggestions for future ILC, and positive notes from implementation. The provider's comments mainly focused on the missing sample arrival documents, the responses to the background survey, or other requested background information. All feedback is valuable and is assessed and exploited in activities improvement.

2.6 Processing the data

2.6.1 Pretesting the data

To test the normality of the data the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was applied. The outliers were rejected according to the Grubbs test before calculating the mean. The results which differed more than $5 \times s_{rob}$ or 50 % from the robust mean, were rejected before the statistical results handling. If the result was reported as below the limit of reporting, it was not included in the statistical calculations.

The participants were to report replicate results for all the measurands except impurities. The replicate results were tested using the Cochran's test, which compares the within-laboratory deviation of each participant to the standard deviation of the replicate results of all the participants. The replicate results which differ significantly from others are outliers. The Cochran's test rejects the results having significantly higher within-laboratory deviation than the results in average, regardless their z score evaluation.

More information about the statistical handling of the data is available from the Guide for participant [6].

2.6.2 Assigned values

The robust mean (dry matter, N_{tot} , pH), the median (impurities, conductivity 25: BioCom1, stability), or the mean (bulk density, conductivity 25: BioCom2, organic matter, TOC) of the results reported by the participants was used as the assigned value. For impurities and stability results the assigned values are only informative due to the high deviation or the low number of results (Table 1). Detailed information of the assigned values, their uncertainties and reliability are shown in Appendix 5.

The assigned values based on the robust mean, the median, or the mean are not metrologically traceable values. As it was not possible to have metrologically traceable assigned values, the best available values were selected to be used as the assigned values. The reliability of the assigned values was statistically tested [2, 3].

When the robust mean, the median, or the mean of the results reported by the participants was used as the assigned value the expanded uncertainty (U_{pt} , $k=2$) was calculated using the robust standard deviation or the standard deviation [2, 6]. The uncertainties of the assigned values varied between 0.8 % and 6.2 % (Appendix 5). **After reporting the preliminary results, the informative assigned value for the total impurities BioCom1_Total was changed from 3.70 to 2.80 g/kg DM based on the renewed result handling. This did not affect the performance evaluation of the participants. No other changes have been made to the assigned values.**

2.6.3 Proficiency assessment procedure

The results of this interlaboratory comparison were evaluated with the z scores.

The standard deviation for proficiency assessment was estimated based on the measurand concentration, the results of homogeneity test, the uncertainty of the assigned value, and expanded measurement uncertainties reported by the participants. The standard deviation for proficiency assessment ($2 \times s_{pt}$ at the 95 % confidence level) was set for pH measurements to 0.3 pH units and for the other measurements from 6 % to 20 % depending on the measurands. Due to the high deviation or the low number of the results, no evaluation was given for impurities and stability in the tested samples (Table 1). **After reporting the preliminary results, no changes have been made to the standard deviations of the proficiency assessment values.**

When using the robust mean, the median, or the mean as the assigned value, the reliability was tested according to the criterion $u_{pt} / s_{pt} \leq 0.3$, where u_{pt} is the standard uncertainty of the assigned value and s_{pt} is the standard deviation for proficiency assessment [2, 3]. When testing the reliability of the assigned value the criterion was fulfilled, and the assigned values were considered reliable.

The reliability of the standard deviation for proficiency assessment (s_{pt}) and the corresponding z score was estimated by comparing s_{pt} with the robust standard deviation (s_{rob}) or standard deviation (s) of the reported results (the criterion) [3]. The uniformity criterion s_{rob} (or s) / $s_{pt} \leq 1.2$ was fulfilled for all samples and measurands.

3 Results and conclusions

3.1 Results

The summary of the results is presented in Table 1. The terms in the results table are explained in Appendix 6. The results and the performance of each participant are presented in Appendix 7 and the reported results with their expanded uncertainties ($k=2$) are presented in Appendix 8. The summary of the z scores is shown in Appendix 9 and z scores in the ascending order in Appendix 10.

The robust standard deviations of the results varied from 1.3 to 11.1 % (Table 1). In the previous interlaboratory comparison SIM 15/2018 for soil improver maturity test from the waste compost the following measurands were tested: bulk density, conductivity, dry matter, organic matter and pH [7]. In this ILC the robust standard deviations were somewhat lower for those measurands than in the previous ILC SIM 15/2018, where the deviations varied from 2.2 % to 17.2 %.

Table 1. The summary of the results in the interlaboratory comparison B2B 12/2025.

Measurand	Sample	Unit	Assigned value	Mean	Rob. mean	Median	s_{rob} / s	$s_{rob} / s \%$	2 x Spt %	n_{all}	Acc z %
Bulk density	BioCom1	g/l	549	549	547	540	23	4.3	10	13	85
	BioCom2	g/l	522	522	520	515	22	4.2	10	13	85
Conductivity 25	BioCom1	mS/m	331	339	337	331	38	11.1	20	13	85
	BioCom2	mS/m	357	357	361	354	18	4.9	15	13	85
Dry matter, DM	BioCom1	% by mass	48.6	48.6	48.6	48.6	0.6	1.3	6	14	100
	BioCom2	% by mass	51.4	51.4	51.4	51.1	1.0	1.9	6	14	100
Impurities	BioCom1_Glass	g/kg DM	1.38	1.54	-	1.38	1.06	69.1	-	7	-
	BioCom1_Metal	g/kg DM	0.17	0.32	-	0.17	0.38	120.7	-	7	-
	BioCom1_Plastic	g/kg DM	1.90	1.96	1.92	1.90	1.60	83.0	-	7	-
	BioCom1_Total	g/kg DM	2.80	3.08	3.92	2.80	3.38	86.2	-	7	-
	BioCom2_Glass	g/kg DM	2.19	2.75	-	2.19	1.93	70.2	-	7	-
	BioCom2_Metal	g/kg DM	0.46	0.57	-	0.46	0.59	103.7	-	7	-
	BioCom2_Plastic	g/kg DM	1.30	1.45	1.43	1.30	0.99	69.5	-	7	-
	BioCom2_Total	g/kg DM	4.40	4.32	5.29	4.40	3.88	73.4	-	7	-
N_{tot}	BioCom1_DG	g/kg DM	28.8	28.9	28.8	29.0	2.1	7.2	20	12	100
	BioCom2_DG	g/kg DM	29.8	29.8	29.8	29.9	2.2	7.5	20	12	100

Table 1. The summary of the results in the interlaboratory comparison B2B 12/2025.

Measurand	Sample	Unit	Assigned value	Mean	Rob. mean	Median	s_{rob} / s	$s_{rob} / s \%$	2 x $s_{pt} \%$	n_{all}	Acc z %
Organic matter	BioCom1	% m/m DM	52.8	52.8	52.5	52.5	2.2	4.3	10	13	77
	BioCom2	% m/m DM	54.2	54.2	54.2	53.1	3.0	5.6	10	13	85
pH	BioCom1	pH unit	8.04	8.03	8.04	8.05	0.10	1.3	3.7	14	100
	BioCom2	pH unit	7.72	7.71	7.72	7.70	0.13	1.7	3.9	14	100
Stability	BioCom1	mmol O ₂ /kg OM/h	3.69	5.84	-	3.69	5.54	94.9	-	4	-
	BioCom2	mmol O ₂ /kg OM/h	2.09	2.11	-	2.09	0.49	23.2	-	4	-
TOC	BioCom1_DG	g/kg DM	284	284	284	282	24	8.5	15	10	100
	BioCom2_DG	g/kg DM	285	285	285	282	21	7.4	15	10	100

Rob. mean: the robust mean, s_{rob} : the robust standard deviation, s : the standard deviation, $s_{rob} \%$: the robust standard deviation as percent, $s \%$: the standard deviation as percent, $2 \times s_{pt} \%$: the standard deviation for proficiency assessment at the 95 % confidence level, n_{all} : the number of the participants, Acc z %: the share of results (%), where $|z| \leq 2$.

Table 2. The summary of repeatability based on replicate determinations (ANOVA statistics).

Measurand	Sample	Unit	Assigned value	Mean	s_w	s_b	s_t	$s_w \%$	$s_b \%$	$s_t \%$	s_b/s_w
Bulk density	BioCom1	g/l	549	549	4.28	23.8	24.2	0.78	4.3	4.4	5.6
	BioCom2	g/l	522	522	7.91	21.6	23.0	1.5	4.1	4.4	2.7
Conductivity 25	BioCom1	mS/m	331	339	6.39	36.4	37.0	1.9	11	11	5.7
	BioCom2	mS/m	357	357	4.41	31.3	31.6	1.2	8.6	8.7	7.1
Dry matter, DM	BioCom1	% by mass	48.6	48.6	0.70	0.26	0.75	1.4	0.53	1.5	0.37
	BioCom2	% by mass	51.4	51.4	1.02	0.58	1.17	2.0	1.1	2.3	0.57
N_{tot}	BioCom1_DG	g/kg DM	28.8	28.9	0.74	2.05	2.18	2.5	7.1	7.5	2.8
	BioCom2_DG	g/kg DM	29.8	29.8	0.71	1.91	2.04	2.4	6.4	6.9	2.7
Organic matter	BioCom1	% m/m DM	52.8	52.8	3.16	2.14	3.81	6.1	4.1	7.3	0.68
	BioCom2	% m/m DM	54.2	54.2	1.45	2.55	2.93	2.7	4.7	5.4	1.8
pH	BioCom1		8.04	8.03	0.072	0.097	0.12	0.89	1.2	1.5	1.4
	BioCom2		7.72	7.71	0.059	0.11	0.12	0.77	1.4	1.6	1.8
Stability	BioCom1	mmol O ₂ /kg OM/h	3.69	5.84	1.81	5.39	5.69	31	92	97	3.0
	BioCom2	mmol O ₂ /kg OM/h	2.09	2.11	0.21	0.46	0.510	10	22	24	2.2
TOC	BioCom1_DG	g/kg DM	284	284	7.32	21.1	22.3	2.6	7.4	7.9	2.9
	BioCom2_DG	g/kg DM	285	285	6.40	18.0	19.1	2.2	6.3	6.7	2.8

s_w : repeatability standard error; s_b : between participants' standard error; s_t : reproducibility standard error.

In this ILC the participants reported replicate results for all the measurements, except impurities. The repeatability of replicate results was tested using ANOVA statistical handling (Table 2). The estimation of the robustness of the methods can be estimated using the ratio s_b/s_w . For the robust methods, this ratio should not exceed 3. The robustness criterion was met with 75 % of the results (Table 2).

3.2 Analytical methods

The participants could use different analytical methods for the measurements in the ILC. The responses from the background survey of the analytical methods are shown in Appendix 11. The used analytical methods and results of the participants grouped by methods are shown in more detail in Appendix 12. The statistical comparison of the analytical methods was possible for the data where the number of the results per method was ≥ 5 .

3.2.1 Bulk density

Most of the participants (10) determined bulk density using the standard method EN 13040-1. Three participants reported the use of another method, i.e. national EN 13040-1 version (2008), internal method based on EN 13040-1, or internal method (Appendix 12).

Differences in the application of the method may have contributed to variation in the results. The standard includes steps such as compacting the subsample in a cylinder using a plunger of a specified mass for a specified time. EN 13040-1 also defines the criteria for the equipment used in the analysis. One participant, whose result deviated from the majority, did not report the duration for which the plunger weight was applied in the background survey (Appendix 11).

3.2.2 Conductivity 25

Most of the participants (11) determined conductivity using the standard method EN 13038. Two participants reported the use of other methods, i.e. internal method based on EN 13040-1 or internal method (Appendix 12).

3.2.3 Dry matter, DM

Nine participants determined dry matter using the standard method EN 13040-1. Five participants reported the use of other methods, i.e. standard method EN 13039, internal method based on EN 13040-1, national EN 13040-1 version (2008), in-house method or internal method (Appendix 12).

In the statistical comparison of the analytical methods used, no significant differences were observed between them.

3.2.4 Impurities

Three to five participants determined impurities (glass, metal, plastic) using the technical specification CEN/TS 16202. One to two participants reported the use of other methods, i.e. internal method based on national version (2008) or internal method (Appendix 12). The observed variation in impurity results is primarily related to the heterogeneous distribution of the impurities within the material.

Impurities such as glass or metal fragments occur sporadically and differ widely in size and mass, meaning they are unevenly distributed even if the bulk matrix appears homogenous. A random inclusion of a single large particle can substantially affect the measured impurity content, which may lead to differences between subsamples.

Subsample size also likely contributed to the observed variability. Participants reported using sample masses ranging from 50 g to 1000 g (Appendix 11), and although results are expressed per kg of dry matter, smaller subsamples have a lower probability of capturing a representative assortment of impurity particles. Larger subsamples increase the likelihood of reflecting the impurity profile of the bulk material more consistently. Differences in subsample mass may therefore have influenced the comparability across the laboratories.

The variation observed is consistent with the results of the Draft prEN 16202:2025 standardisation interlaboratory studies [8]. This alignment indicates that such variability is characteristic of impurity determinations in heterogeneous compost materials rather than specific to this study.

3.2.5 Total nitrogen, N_{tot}

Two of the participants determined total nitrogen using the standard method EN 13654-1 and four participants using the standard method EN 13654-2. Six participants reported the use of other methods i.e. national EN 16168 (2012), internal method, internal method based on ISO 11261 (1995) and EN 16169 (2012), or Kjeldahl method (Appendix 12).

3.2.6 Organic matter

Most of the participants (10) determined organic matter using the standard method EN 13039. Three participants reported the use of other methods, i.e. national EN 13040-1 version (2008), internal method based on EN 13039, or internal method (Appendix 12). Two participants reported considerably lower organic matter results compared to the rest. One of these participants later indicated, that the result had been reported on a fresh-matter basis rather than on a dry-matter basis as requested (Appendix 4). The other participants did not provide an explanation. Apart from these cases, the remaining results showed only minor variation, which may be attributed to the heterogeneous nature of the material, including the presence of inorganic particles such as rocks in subsamples.

3.2.7 pH

Most of the participants (12) determined pH using the standard method EN 13037. Two participants reported the use of other methods, i.e. internal method based on EN 13037 or internal method (Appendix 12).

3.2.8 Stability

Stability was tested by the oxygen uptake rate, OUR, using the standard method EN 16087-1. Four participants reported the results of stability (Appendix 12.) Most of the participants reported significantly lower OUR values compared to the homogeneity study.

Several factors may have contributed to these differences. During transport, the samples were in contact with a frozen cold pack, which may have temporarily reduced microbial activity or affected temperature-sensitive microorganisms. Some participants also reported shorter pre-mixing times (0–4 h) than specified in the standard method (4–8 h), which may have limited the reactivation of microbial activity prior to measurement (Appendix 11). Reported measurement temperatures varied between 20 °C and 30 °C, and lower temperatures are generally associated with lower OUR because microbial processes slow down as temperature decreases (Appendix 11).

Some variation may also be linked to the manual selection of the linear portion of the measurement curve, which forms the basis for calculating the results. Although this step follows the guidance of the standard method, it relies on visual assessment as no more objective or automated procedure is available for defining the linear region. In addition, the calculation of OUR results by each laboratory involves several sample-specific and instrument-specific parameters including bottle volume, the pressure drops and corresponding measurement time, and the concentrations of organic matter and dry matter. These parameters require precise and consistent application. As only four laboratories submitted OUR results, the stability comparison should be interpreted as indicative.

3.2.9 Total organic carbon, TOC

Two participants determined TOC using the method CEN/TS 17776. Eight participants reported the use of other methods i.e. national version EN 15936 (withdrawn, 2012) or EN 15936 (2022), internal method, EN 15936 (2022) and SFS-EN 13137 (withdrawn, 2001), EN ISO 15936A (2022), or internal method (Appendix 12).

3.3 Uncertainties of the reported results

Together with their results, the participants were required to report the expanded uncertainties ($k=2$) as a percentage. Six to eight of the participants reported the measurement uncertainty with at least some of their results (Table 3, Appendix 13).

The most used approach to evaluate measurement uncertainty was based on data obtained from method validation. A few participants used internal quality control data and/or proficiency test data (Appendix 13). Other approaches used included, for example, parallel results, results obtained from proficiency tests, standard deviations, or other internal methods. Depending on the sample and measurand, up to two participants used MUKIT measurement uncertainty software for the evaluation of their uncertainties, which is available on the webpage: syke.fi/envical/en [9, 10]. Generally, the approach used for evaluating the measurement uncertainty did not have definite impact on the uncertainty evaluations.

It was evident that some uncertainties had been reported erroneously (for example pH, organic matter), not as a relative value (%) as the ILC organizer had requested (Table 3). Within the optimal measuring range, the expanded measurement uncertainty ($k=2$) should typically be 10 – 30 %. Close to the limit of quantification the relative measurement uncertainty is higher. The expanded uncertainties below 5 % could commonly be considered unrealistic uncertainty value for routine laboratories. Further, the number of significant digits should correlate with the significant digits of the reported result.

Table 3. The ranges of the expanded uncertainties (U_i , $k = 2$) reported by participants, expressed as percentages.

Measurand	U_i %
Bulk density	2.66-20
Conductivity 25	10-25
Dry matter	3-10
N_{tot}	10-50
Organic matter	2.6-25
pH	1.6-6.50 (0.1-0.5 pH unit)
TOC	4.76-30

4 Evaluation of the results

The performance evaluation of the participants was based on the z scores, which were calculated using the assigned values and the standard deviation for proficiency assessment (Table 4 and Appendix 6).

Table 4. Assessment of the z scores.

Criteria for z scores	Assessment
$ z \leq 2.0$	Satisfactory
$2.0 < z < 3.0$	Questionable
$ z \geq 3.0$	Unsatisfactory

In total, 93 % of the results were satisfactory when total deviation of 0.3 pH units for pH values and for the other measurements 6–20 % from the assigned value was accepted (Appendix 9). Five participants used accredited analytical methods for at least part of the measurands, and all those results (100 %) were satisfactory. The summary of the performance evaluation is presented in Table 5. Table 5 also includes a comparison to the previous ILC SIM 15/2018, where partly the same measurands (bulk density, conductivity, dry matter, organic matter, and pH) were tested from the compost [7].

Table 5. Summary of the performance evaluation in the interlaboratory comparison B2B 12/2025.

Sample	Satisfactory results (%)	Accepted deviation from the assigned value (%)	Remarks
BioCom1	89	3.7–20	Good performance. Stability was not evaluated (see 2.6.3). In the SIM 15/2018 the performance was satisfactory for 98 % of the results, when accepting deviation of 6.5-50 % from the assigned value [7].
BioCom1_DG	100	15 – 20	Excellent performance.
BioCom2	91	3.9 – 15	Very good performance. Stability was not evaluated (see 2.6.3). In the SIM 15/2018 the performance was satisfactory for 95 % of the results, when accepting deviation of 8.5-50 % from the assigned value [7].
BioCom2_DG	100	15 – 20	Excellent performance.

5 Summary

Finnish Food Authority, in collaboration with ProfTest Syke's proficiency testing services, organised an interlaboratory comparison (ILC) in October-November 2025 (B2B 12/2025) for the analysis of quality parameters in biowaste compost. The following measurands were tested from two biowaste compost samples: pH, dry matter (DM), bulk density, electrical conductivity, impurities (IMP), total nitrogen (N_{tot}), organic matter, total organic carbon (TOC), and stability (oxygen uptake rate, OUR). This ILC was part of EU co-funded Bin2Bean project (bin2bean.eu). A total of 14 laboratories participated in this interlaboratory comparison.

The robust mean, the mean, or the median of the results reported by the participants was used as the assigned value for the measurands. The uncertainties of the assigned values were estimated at the 95 % confidence level ($k=2$) and they varied between 0.8 % and 6.2 %.

The performance evaluation was based on the z scores. In total, 93 % of the results were satisfactory when total deviation of 0.3 pH units for pH values and for the other measurements 6–20 % from the assigned value was accepted at the 95 % confidence level. Five participants used accredited analytical methods at least for a part of the measurements and all those results were satisfactory.

The compliance of products covered by the EU Fertilising Products Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 can be demonstrated using harmonised reference standard methods. At the time of the interlaboratory comparison, the new versions of these methods were still under development [11]. Therefore, participating laboratories used earlier standard versions or validated in-house procedures.

The results indicate two main sources of variability. The first source relates to the intrinsic properties of the biowaste-based composts. These materials are naturally heterogeneous, which was evident in the impurity determinations where the uneven distribution of particles such as glass and metal strongly affected the results depending on the test portion selected. The stability measurement was influenced by sample's biological properties, as the OUR parameter is sensitive to temperature changes and requires sufficient time for microbial activity to recover before analysis.

The second source of variability was related to procedural differences between laboratories. These included, for example, differences in the test portion size used in impurity analysis, differences in pre-mixing time and measurement temperature in the OUR test, and other deviations from the standard procedures reported by the participants. These observations depicted in this report reveal the critical procedure steps affecting result reproducibility. This will help laboratories to focus on the stages that require particular attention when implementing the forthcoming reference standards or aligning in-house methods in the future.

6 Summary in Finnish

Ruokavirasto järjesti yhteistyössä Proftest Syke vertailumittaustoiminnan kanssa laboratorioden välisen vertailumittauksen loka-marraskuussa 2025 (B2B 12/2025) laboratorioille, jotka tekevät biojätekompostien laatuparametrimäärytyksiä. Kahdesta biojätekompostinäytteestä testattiin seuraavat määrytykset: pH, kuiva-aine (DM), tilavuuspaino, sähkönjohtavuus, epäpuhtaudet (IMP), kokonaistyyppi (N_{tot}), orgaaninen aines (TOC) ja stabiilisuus (hapenkulutus, OUR). Vertailumittaukseen osallistui yhteensä 14 laboratoriota.

Testisuureen vertailuarvona käytettiin osallistujien tulosten robustia keskiarvoa, keskiarvoa tai mediaania. Osallistujien pätevyuden arviointi tehtiin z-arvojen avulla. Koko tulosaineistossa oli 93 % hyväksyttäviä tuloksia, kun vertailuarvosta sallittiin pH-määrytyksissä 0,3 pH-yksikön ja muissa määrytyksissä 6–20 %:n poikkeama. Viisi osallistujaa käytti akkreditoitua menetelmää ainakin osassa määrytyksistä ja kaikki nämä tulokset olivat hyväksyttäviä.

EU:n lannoitevalmisteasetuksen (EU) 2019/1009 mukaisten tuotteiden vaatimustenmukaisuus voidaan osoittaa harmonisoiduilla referenssistandardimenetelmillä, joiden uusien versioiden valmistelu oli vielä kesken vertailumittauksen aikaan [11]. Siksi osallistuneet laboratoriot käyttivät aiempia standardiversioita tai validoituja omia menetelmiä.

Vertailumittauksen tuloksista havaittiin kaksi pääasiallista tulosvaihtelun lähettä. Ensimmäinen lähde liittyy biopohjaisten kompostien luontaisiin ominaisuuksiin. Nämä materiaalit ovat luonnostaan heterogeenisiä, mikä näkyi epäpuhtausmäärytyksissä. Lasin ja metallin kaltaisten partikkelien epätasainen jakautuminen aiheutti merkittävää vaihtelua tuloksiin riippuen testaukseen valitusta osanäytteestä. Biokompostin stabiilisuuden määrittämiseen vaikutti puolestaan näytteen biologinen aktiivisuus, sillä OUR-parametri on herkkä lämpötilavaihteluille ja edellyttää riittävän pitkää aikaa mikrobiyhteisön toiminnan palautumiselle ennen mittauksen suorittamista.

Toinen havaittu vaihtelun lähde liittyi laboratorioden välisiin menetelmällisiin eroihin. Näihin sisältyivät muun muassa epäpuhtausmäärytyksissä käytetyn testiosuuden koon vaihtelut, esisekoitusajan ja mittaustilanteiden erot OUR-testissä sekä osallistujien raportoimat muut poikkeamat standardimenetelmistä. Tässä raportissa esitetyt havainnot osoittavat ne analyysiprosessin kriittiset vaiheet, joilla on olennainen vaikutus tulosten toistettavuuteen. Näiden kriittisten vaiheiden tunnistaminen tukee laboratorioita kohdentamaan menetelmäkehityksen ja laadunvarmistuksen toimenpiteet niihin prosessin osa-alueisiin, jotka edellyttävät erityistä tarkkuutta joko tulevien viitestandardien käyttöönotossa tai laboratorioden omien menetelmien harmonisointiprosessissa.

References

1. SFS-EN ISO 17043, 2010. Conformity assessment – General requirements for Proficiency Testing.
2. ISO 13528, 2022. Statistical methods for use in proficiency testing by interlaboratory comparisons.
3. Thompson, M., Ellison, S. L. R., Wood, R., 2006. The International Harmonized Protocol for the Proficiency Testing of Analytical Chemistry laboratories (IUPAC Technical report). Pure Appl. Chem. 78: 145-196, iupac.org.
4. SFS-EN 12579, 2024. Soil improvers and growing media. Sampling.
5. SFS-EN 13040, 2008. Maanparannusaineet ja kasvualustat. Näytteen esikäsittely kemiallisia ja fysikaalisia kokeita varten, kuiva-ainepitoisuuden, kosteuspitoisuuden ja tiivistetyn laboratoriotilavuuspainon määrittäminen.
6. ProfTest Syke, Guide for participants: syke.fi/proftest/en → Current proficiency tests and interlaboratory comparisons. https://www.syke.fi/sites/default/files/documents/ProfTest%20Syke_Guide%20for%20participants%202025.pdf.
7. Maunuksela, L., Pelkonen, A., Björklöf, K., Ilmakunnas, M., Kartio M. and Leivuori, M. Interlaboratory Comparison Test 15/2018. Soil improver maturity test. Reports of the Finnish Environment 25/2018. (<http://hdl.handle.net/10138/256035>).
8. Draft prEN 16202, 2025. Soil improvers and growing media — Determination of the content of macroscopic impurities and stones.
9. Näykki, T., Virtanen, A. and Leito, I., 2012. Software support for the Nordtest method of measurement uncertainty evaluation. Accred. Qual. Assur. 17: 603-612. MUKIT website: syke.fi/envical.
10. Magnusson B., Näykki T., Hovind H., Krysell M., Sahlin E., 2017. Handbook for Calculation of Measurement Uncertainty in Environmental Laboratories. Nordtest Report TR 537 (ed. 4), nordtest.info.
11. Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising products. EUR-Lex. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/1009/oj>.

Appendix 1. Participants in the interlaboratory comparison

Country	Participant
Belgium	Innolab BV
Finland	Finnish Food Authority HAMK Häme University of Applied Sciences KVVY Tutkimus Oy, Tampere MetropoliLab Oy Natural Resources Institute Finland Savonia-ammattikorkeakoulu oy SGS Finland Oy, Kotka
France	Eurofins Galys
Germany	LUFA Nord-West, Institut für Boden und Umwelt
Greece	Polyeco S.A. Qlab -Research, Analytical and Quality Control Lab
Italy	Centro Ricerche Produzioni Animali Soc. Cons. p. A.
Spain	Eurofins Analisis Agro, S.A.

Appendix 2. Sample preparation

Sample collection procedure

Two compost samples were obtained from a composting facility. For each sample, the collection process was as follows:

- A single compost pile was selected. Approximately 15 sampling points were created by removing the surface layer with a shovel to avoid contamination.
- From each point, 10 l material was collected to obtain a total of approximately 150 l of material. All collected material was combined on a tarpaulin and thoroughly mixed to ensure homogeneity.
- The material was placed in plastic bags and transported to the Finnish Food Authority's laboratory for further processing.

Sample preparation protocol

1. Homogenization and sieving

Sample material was homogenized and sieved using a 10 mm mesh. Particles retained on the sieve were discarded.

2. Portioning

The sieved material (<10 mm) was thoroughly mixed and portioned into 3-liter batches for each participant by adding one 0.5-liter scoop at a time. These batches were labelled BioCom1 and BioCom2. Additionally, part of the sieved material was divided into 1.2 kg bags using the same method and labelled BioCom1_IMP and BioCom2_IMP.

3. Drying and grinding

Approximately 2 kg of each sieved sample was dried at 40 °C for 2-3 days until completely dry. The dried material was sieved through a 2 mm mesh, and particles smaller than 2 mm were ground using a ball mill. These dried and ground samples were packed into small plastic bottles and labelled BioCom1_DG and BioCom2_DG.

4. Packing and shipping

Samples were packed in boxes with cooling elements and shipped to the participating laboratories.

Appendix 3. Homogeneity of the samples

Criteria for homogeneity (parallel results):

$S_{\text{analytical}} / S_{\text{pt}} < 0.5$ and $S_{\text{sam}}^2 < c$, where

$S_{\text{analytical}}$ = analytical deviation, standard deviation of the results in a sub sample

S_{h} = standard deviation for homogeneity test

S_{pt} = standard deviation for proficiency assessment

S_{sam} = between-sample deviation, standard deviation of results between sub samples

$c = F1 \times S_{\text{all}}^2 + F2 \times S_{\text{analytical}}^2$, where

$S_{\text{all}}^2 = (0.3 \times S_{\text{h}})^2$

F1 and F2 are constants of F distribution derived from the standard statistical tables for the tested number of samples [2, 3].

Table 1. Homogeneity test results of samples BioCom1 and BioCom2.

Measurand Unit	Sample	Concentration	n	S_{h} %	S_{h}	S_{pt} %	$S_{\text{analytical}}$	$S_{\text{analytical}} / S_{\text{h}}$	$S_{\text{analytical}} / S_{\text{h}} < 0.5?$	S_{sam}^2	c	$S_{\text{sam}}^2 < c?$
Bulk density g/l	BioCom1	538	5	1.5	8.06	5	3.14	0.39	✓	31.0	34.5	✓
	BioCom2	512	5	1.5	7.68	5	2.81	0.37	✓	< 0.001	29.1	✓
Conductivity 25 mS/m	BioCom1	319	5	5	15.9	10	6.90	0.43	✓	< 0.001	154	✓
	BioCom2	341	5	3.0	10.2	7.5	4.39	0.43	✓	9.16	62.7	✓
Dry matter, DM % by mass	BioCom1	49.0	4	3.0	1.47	3	0.66	0.44	✓	< 0.001	1.73	✓
	BioCom2	51.0	5	1.5	0.76	3	0.25	0.33	✓	0.11	0.25	✓
Organic matter % m/m DM	BioCom1	49.1	4	3.0	1.47	5	0.65	0.44	✓	< 0.001	1.69	✓
	BioCom2	54.9	4	4.0	2.19	5	0.55	0.25	✓	0.41	1.98	✓
pH	BioCom1	8.05	5	1.5	0.12	1.85	0.05	0.44	✓	0.002	0.01	✓
	BioCom2	7.78	5	1.0	0.08	1.95	0.02	0.25	✓	< 0.001	0.002	✓
Stability mmol O ₂ /kg OM/h	BioCom1	15.2	4	16	2.43	-	1.08	0.44	✓	0.86	4.65	✓
	BioCom2	13.9	3	28	3.89	-	1.70	0.44	✓	< 0.001	16.4	✓

✓: The homogeneity criterion is met, ✗: The homogeneity criterion is not met.

Criterion for homogeneity of single result

Table 2. Homogeneity test results for total nitrogen (N_{tot})

Measurand, Unit	Sample	Concentration	n	S _{pt} %	S _{pt}	0.5 x S _{pt}	S _{sam}	S _{sam} /S _{pt} < 0.5?
N _{tot} , g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG	26.0	5	10	2.60	1.30	0.40	✓
N _{tot} , g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG	27.3	5	10	2.73	1.37	0.40	✓

✓: The homogeneity criterion is met, ✗: The homogeneity criterion is not met.

Conclusion: The samples may be regarded as homogeneous, as all tested samples and measurands met the criteria of the homogeneity test.

Appendix 4. Feedback from the interlaboratory comparison

Feedback from the participants

Participant	Comments on technical execution	Action / Organiser
3	ILC was fine and easy to upload results.	The organiser thanks you for the feedback.
6	The participant suggested using less stable matrices in future interlaboratory tests. In this ILC, the OUR test results for the BioCom1 and BioCom2 samples were very close to the instrument's detection limits.	The provider acknowledged the suggestion and will take it consideration in the future ILCs.
6	The participant requested permission to share their performance on their professional network on LinkedIn after the preliminary results report was published.	The preliminary results report is confidential and intended solely for use within participant's laboratory. Its purpose is to allow participants to comment on the data handling, particularly if the organiser has made any errors. Data handling may be revised if feedback from participants requires it. The confidentiality of the preliminary results report is outlined in the report, and any online summaries of the data online are not permitted.
10	The participant asked if they could report their results without including measurement uncertainty, because they normally did not calculate or use it. They also asked how they should report the results from the other method they used.	There is an option to report the results without including measurement uncertainty. The provider also gave guidance on how to report the results from the other method that was used. In addition, the background survey included a section where the method applied could be described.
10	Suggestions for additional measurand to test biogas methane potential and residual biogas potential.	The provider acknowledged the suggestion and will take it consideration in the future ILCs.
12	Everything was fine.	The organiser thanks you for the feedback.
All	The participants expressed interest in participating in a similar interlaboratory comparison in the future.	The organiser thanks you for the feedback and will look for opportunities to a similar kind of ILC in the future.

Participant	Comments to the results	Action / Organiser
3	The participant reported results for organic matter in the wrong unit (fresh material instead of dry matter). The correct results should be for organic matter: BioCom1 57.89 % m/m DM BioCom2 58.31 % m/m DM	The results were outliers in the statistical treatment and thus did not affect the performance evaluation. If the results had been reported correctly, the evaluation of the results would have been satisfactory. The participant can re-calculate the z scores according to the Guide for participants [4].

Feedback to the participants

Participant	Comments
5, 7, 10, 14	The participants did not return the sample arrival document to the organizer. The participants should follow the instructions of the organizer.
11, 14	The participants did not answer the background survey. The participants should follow the instructions of the organiser.
3, 9	The participants did not inform the accreditation status of their method for some measurands. The participants should follow the instructions of the organiser.
7, 8, 9, 11, 14	Some of the participants' results were Cochran outliers (Part. 7: BioCom2: dry matter, BioCom1: organic matter; Part. 8: BioCom1: bulk density; Part. 9: BioCom2: conductivity; Part. 11: BioCom1: pH; Part. 14: BioCom1: N _{tot}). The participants are recommended to check the allowed difference for the parallel results.
4, 12, 15	Some participants indicated that they reported absolute measurement uncertainty together with their results, but the request from the organizer was to report the relative measurement uncertainty. The participants should follow the instructions of the organiser.
13	The participant reported a total impurities value that was considerably higher than the results for the individual impurities tested. The participant is recommended to verify their method.
8, 9	A small sample amount in the determination of impurities affects the results, and the amount of sample used does not comply with the standards. Participants are recommended to verify their method.

Appendix 5. Assigned values and their uncertainties

Measurand	Sample	Unit	Assigned value	U _{pt}	U _{pt} , %	Determination of assigned value	u _{pt} /s _{pt}
Bulk density	BioCom1	g/l	549	14	2.6	Mean	0.26
	BioCom2	g/l	522	14	2.6	Mean	0.26
Conductivity 25	BioCom1	mS/m	331	21	6.2	Median	0.31
	BioCom2	mS/m	357	10	2.7	Mean	0.18
Dry matter, DM	BioCom1	% by mass	48.6	0.4	0.8	Robust mean	0.13
	BioCom2	% by mass	51.4	0.7	1.3	Robust mean	0.22
Impurities, IMP ¹⁾	BioCom1_Glass	g/kg DM	1.38	-	-	Median	-
	BioCom1_Metal	g/kg DM	0.17	-	-	Median	-
	BioCom1_Plastic	g/kg DM	1.90	-	-	Median	-
	BioCom1_Total	g/kg DM	2.80	-	-	Median	-
	BioCom2_Glass	g/kg DM	2.19	-	-	Median	-
	BioCom2_Metal	g/kg DM	0.46	-	-	Median	-
	BioCom2_Plastic	g/kg DM	1.30	-	-	Median	-
	BioCom2_Total	g/kg DM	4.40	-	-	Median	-
N _{tot}	BioCom1_DG	g/kg DM	28.8	1.5	5.2	Robust mean	0.26
	BioCom2_DG	g/kg DM	29.8	1.6	5.4	Robust mean	0.27
Organic matter	BioCom1	% m/m DM	52.8	1.1	2.1	Mean	0.21
	BioCom2	% m/m DM	54.2	1.7	3.1	Mean	0.31
pH	BioCom1		8.04	0.07	0.9	Robust mean	0.24
	BioCom2		7.72	0.08	1.1	Robust mean	0.28
Stability ¹⁾	BioCom1	mmol O ₂ /kg OM/h	3.69	-	-	Median	-
	BioCom2	mmol O ₂ /kg OM/h	2.09	-	-	Median	-
TOC	BioCom1_DG	g/kg DM	284	14	4.8	Mean	0.32
	BioCom2_DG	g/kg DM	285	12	4.1	Mean	0.27

¹⁾ Informative assigned value (see chapter 2.6.2).

U_{pt} = Expanded uncertainty of the assigned value

Criterion for reliability of the assigned value $u_{pt}/s_{pt} < 0.3$, where

s_{pt} = the standard deviation for proficiency assessment

u_{pt} = standard uncertainty of the assigned value

If $u_{pt}/s_{pt} < 0.3$, the assigned value is reliable.

Appendix 6. Terms in the results tables

The information could be applied according to the ILC.

Measurand	The tested parameter
Sample	The code of the sample
Assigned value	The value attributed to a particular property of an ILC item
Participant's result	The result reported by the participant (when replicate results are reported, the mean value)
$2 \times s_{pt}$ %	The standard deviation for proficiency assessment (s_{pt}) at the 95 % confidence level
z score	Used for the participant's performance evaluation in the ILC. Calculated with formula:

$$z = (x_i - x_{pt})/s_{pt}, \text{ where}$$

x_i = the result of the individual participant

x_{pt} = the assigned value

s_{pt} = the standard deviation for proficiency assessment

Assessment of the z scores

$ z \leq 2.0$	Satisfactory
$2.0 < z < 3.0$	Questionable (warning signal), the result deviates more than $2 \times s_{pt}$ from the assigned value.
$ z \geq 3.0$	Unsatisfactory (action signal), the result deviates more than $3 \times s_{pt}$ from the assigned value.

E_n score	Error, normalized – Used to evaluate the difference between the assigned value and participant's result within their claimed expanded uncertainty. Calculated with formula:
-------------------------------	---

$$(E_n)_i = \frac{x_i - x_{pt}}{\sqrt{U_i^2 + U_{pt}^2}}, \text{ where}$$

U_i = the expanded uncertainty of a participant's result

U_{pt} = the expanded uncertainty of the assigned value

Assessment of the E_n scores

$ E_n \leq 1.0$	Satisfactory, should be taken as an indicator of successful performance when the uncertainties are valid.
$ E_n > 1.0$	Unsatisfactory (action signal), could indicate a need to review the uncertainty estimates, or to correct a measurement issue.

Md	Median
s	Standard deviation
s %	Standard deviation, %
n_{stat}	Number of results in statistical processing

More information of the statistical calculations in international standards ISO/IEC 17043 and ISO 13528 as well as in ProfTest Syke Guide for participants [1, 2, 6].

Appendix 7. Results of each participant

Participant 1												
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2×s _{pt} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}
Bulk density	g/l	BioCom1		2.79	549	10	626	540	549	24	4.4	11
	g/l	BioCom2		3.10	522	10	603	515	522	22	4.3	11
Conductivity 25	mS/m	BioCom1		2.52	331	20	415	331	339	37	10.8	12
	mS/m	BioCom2		1.05	357	15	385	354	357	16	4.5	11
Dry matter, DM	% by mass	BioCom1		0.31	48.6	6	49.1	48.6	48.6	0.6	1.2	14
	% by mass	BioCom2		-0.26	51.4	6	51.0	51.1	51.4	0.9	1.8	14
pH		BioCom1		-0.61	8.04	3.7	7.95	8.05	8.03	0.11	1.4	14
		BioCom2		-0.46	7.72	3.9	7.65	7.70	7.71	0.12	1.5	14
TOC	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		1.78	284	15	322	282	284	22	7.6	10
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		1.33	285	15	313	282	285	19	6.5	10

Participant 2												
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2×s _{pt} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}
Bulk density	g/l	BioCom1		-0.40	549	10	538	540	549	24	4.4	11
	g/l	BioCom2		0.29	522	10	530	515	522	22	4.3	11
Conductivity 25	mS/m	BioCom1		-9.99	331	20	0.32	331	339	37	10.8	12
	mS/m	BioCom2		-13.32	357	15	0.34	354	357	16	4.5	11
Dry matter, DM	% by mass	BioCom1		-0.23	48.6	6	48.3	48.6	48.6	0.6	1.2	14
	% by mass	BioCom2		1.16	51.4	6	53.2	51.1	51.4	0.9	1.8	14
N _{tot}	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		-0.03	28.8	20	28.7	29.0	28.9	2.1	7.3	12
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		-0.12	29.8	20	29.5	29.9	29.8	2.0	6.6	12
Organic matter	% m/m DM	BioCom1		-10.05	52.8	10	26.3	52.5	52.8	1.7	3.3	10
	% m/m DM	BioCom2		-10.15	54.2	10	26.7	53.1	54.2	2.7	5.1	11
pH		BioCom1		0.57	8.04	3.7	8.13	8.05	8.03	0.11	1.4	14
		BioCom2		0.73	7.72	3.9	7.83	7.70	7.71	0.12	1.5	14
TOC	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		-1.18	284	15	259	282	284	22	7.6	10
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		-1.00	285	15	264	282	285	19	6.5	10

Participant 3												
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2×s _{pt} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}
Bulk density	g/l	BioCom1		0.08	549	10	551	540	549	24	4.4	11
	g/l	BioCom2		-0.25	522	10	515	515	522	22	4.3	11
Conductivity 25	mS/m	BioCom1		0.82	331	20	358	331	339	37	10.8	12
	mS/m	BioCom2		0.64	357	15	374	354	357	16	4.5	11
Dry matter, DM	% by mass	BioCom1		-0.30	48.6	6	48.2	48.6	48.6	0.6	1.2	14
	% by mass	BioCom2		-0.35	51.4	6	50.9	51.1	51.4	0.9	1.8	14
Impurities, IMP	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Glass			1.38		2.18	1.38	1.54	1.06	69.1	5
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Metal			0.17		0.97	0.17	0.32	0.38	120.7	5
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Plastic			1.90		2.87	1.90	1.96	1.49	75.8	7
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Total			2.80		6.02	2.80	3.08	2.16	70.2	6
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Glass			2.19		5.62	2.19	2.75	1.93	70.2	6
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Metal			0.46		1.33	0.46	0.57	0.59	103.7	4
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Plastic			1.30		1.22	1.30	1.45	0.93	63.8	7
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Total			4.40		8.17	4.40	4.32	2.48	57.4	6

Participant 3												
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2*s _{pt} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}
N _{tot}	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		-0.75	28.8	20	26.7	29.0	28.9	2.1	7.3	12
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		-0.91	29.8	20	27.1	29.9	29.8	2.0	6.6	12
Organic matter	% m/m DM	BioCom1		-9.76	52.8	10	27.0	52.5	52.8	1.7	3.3	10
	% m/m DM	BioCom2		-9.06	54.2	10	29.6	53.1	54.2	2.7	5.1	11
pH		BioCom1		0.40	8.04	3.7	8.10	8.05	8.03	0.11	1.4	14
		BioCom2		0.60	7.72	3.9	7.81	7.70	7.71	0.12	1.5	14
Stability	mmol O2/kg OM/h	BioCom1			3.69		2.00	3.69	5.84	5.54	94.9	4
	mmol O2/kg OM/h	BioCom2			2.09		2.60	2.09	2.11	0.49	23.2	3
TOC	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		1.29	284	15	311	282	284	22	7.6	10
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		0.78	285	15	302	282	285	19	6.5	10

Participant 4												
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2*s _{pt} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}
Bulk density	g/l	BioCom1		-0.31	549	10	540	540	549	24	4.4	11
	g/l	BioCom2		-0.31	522	10	514	515	522	22	4.3	11
Conductivity 25	mS/m	BioCom1		0.22	331	20	338	331	339	37	10.8	12
	mS/m	BioCom2		0.25	357	15	364	354	357	16	4.5	11
Dry matter, DM	% by mass	BioCom1		-0.74	48.6	6	47.5	48.6	48.6	0.6	1.2	14
	% by mass	BioCom2		-0.60	51.4	6	50.5	51.1	51.4	0.9	1.8	14
Impurities, IMP	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Glass			1.38		2.97	1.38	1.54	1.06	69.1	5
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Metal			0.17		0.17	0.17	0.32	0.38	120.7	5
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Plastic			1.90		1.75	1.90	1.96	1.49	75.8	7
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Total			2.80		4.90	2.80	3.08	2.16	70.2	6
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Glass			2.19		1.78	2.19	2.75	1.93	70.2	6
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Metal			0.46		0.20	0.46	0.57	0.59	103.7	4
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Plastic			1.30		1.30	1.30	1.45	0.93	63.8	7
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Total			4.40		3.30	4.40	4.32	2.48	57.4	6
N _{tot}	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		-0.85	28.8	20	26.3	29.0	28.9	2.1	7.3	12
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		-0.83	29.8	20	27.3	29.9	29.8	2.0	6.6	12
Organic matter	% m/m DM	BioCom1		0.58	52.8	10	54.3	52.5	52.8	1.7	3.3	10
	% m/m DM	BioCom2		0.90	54.2	10	56.6	53.1	54.2	2.7	5.1	11
pH		BioCom1		0.71	8.04	3.7	8.15	8.05	8.03	0.11	1.4	14
		BioCom2		-0.10	7.72	3.9	7.71	7.70	7.71	0.12	1.5	14
Stability	mmol O2/kg OM/h	BioCom1			3.69		14.00	3.69	5.84	5.54	94.9	4
	mmol O2/kg OM/h	BioCom2			2.09		10.9	2.09	2.11	0.49	23.2	3

Participant 5												
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2*s _{pt} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}
Bulk density	g/l	BioCom1		0.80	549	10	571	540	549	24	4.4	11
	g/l	BioCom2		1.11	522	10	551	515	522	22	4.3	11
Conductivity 25	mS/m	BioCom1		0.97	331	20	363	331	339	37	10.8	12
	mS/m	BioCom2		0.39	357	15	368	354	357	16	4.5	11
Dry matter, DM	% by mass	BioCom1		-0.08	48.6	6	48.5	48.6	48.6	0.6	1.2	14
	% by mass	BioCom2		0.07	51.4	6	51.5	51.1	51.4	0.9	1.8	14
N _{tot}	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		0.78	28.8	20	31.0	29.0	28.9	2.1	7.3	12
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		0.75	29.8	20	32.0	29.9	29.8	2.0	6.6	12
Organic matter	% m/m DM	BioCom1		-0.12	52.8	10	52.5	52.5	52.8	1.7	3.3	10
	% m/m DM	BioCom2		-0.45	54.2	10	53.0	53.1	54.2	2.7	5.1	11

Participant 5												
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2*s _{pt} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}
pH		BioCom1		-0.27	8.04	3.7	8.00	8.05	8.03	0.11	1.4	14
		BioCom2		-0.03	7.72	3.9	7.72	7.70	7.71	0.12	1.5	14
TOC	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		-0.11	284	15	282	282	284	22	7.6	10
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		0.28	285	15	291	282	285	19	6.5	10

Participant 6												
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2*s _{pt} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}
Stability	mmol O2/kg OM/h	BioCom1		3.69			4.58	3.69	5.84	5.54	94.9	4
	mmol O2/kg OM/h	BioCom2		2.09			1.63	2.09	2.11	0.49	23.2	3

Participant 7												
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2*s _{pt} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}
Bulk density	g/l	BioCom1		1.85	549	10	600	540	549	24	4.4	11
	g/l	BioCom2		1.78	522	10	569	515	522	22	4.3	11
Conductivity 25	mS/m	BioCom1		0.14	331	20	336	331	339	37	10.8	12
	mS/m	BioCom2		-0.11	357	15	354	354	357	16	4.5	11
Dry matter, DM	% by mass	BioCom1		0.52	48.6	6	49.4	48.6	48.6	0.6	1.2	14
	% by mass	BioCom2		0.96	51.4	6	52.9	51.1	51.4	0.9	1.8	14
N _{tot}	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		0.14	28.8	20	29.2	29.0	28.9	2.1	7.3	12
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		0.50	29.8	20	31.3	29.9	29.8	2.0	6.6	12
Organic matter	% m/m DM	BioCom1		-3.30	52.8	10	44.1	52.5	52.8	1.7	3.3	10
	% m/m DM	BioCom2		-0.99	54.2	10	51.5	53.1	54.2	2.7	5.1	11
pH		BioCom1		-1.82	8.04	3.7	7.77	8.05	8.03	0.11	1.4	14
		BioCom2		-1.03	7.72	3.9	7.57	7.70	7.71	0.12	1.5	14
TOC	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		-0.68	284	15	270	282	284	22	7.6	10
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		-0.82	285	15	268	282	285	19	6.5	10

Participant 8												
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2*s _{pt} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}
Bulk density	g/l	BioCom1		0.70	549	10	568	540	549	24	4.4	11
	g/l	BioCom2		-0.21	522	10	517	515	522	22	4.3	11
Conductivity 25	mS/m	BioCom1		-0.58	331	20	312	331	339	37	10.8	12
	mS/m	BioCom2		-1.30	357	15	322	354	357	16	4.5	11
Dry matter, DM	% by mass	BioCom1		0.00	48.6	6	48.6	48.6	48.6	0.6	1.2	14
	% by mass	BioCom2		-0.32	51.4	6	50.9	51.1	51.4	0.9	1.8	14
Impurities, IMP	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Glass			1.38		0.25	1.38	1.54	1.06	69.1	5
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Metal			0.17		0.03	0.17	0.32	0.38	120.7	5
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Plastic			1.90		0.12	1.90	1.96	1.49	75.8	7
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Total			2.80		0.40	2.80	3.08	2.16	70.2	6
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Glass			2.19		0.30	2.19	2.75	1.93	70.2	6
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Metal			0.46		<0.01	0.46	0.57	0.59	103.7	4
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Plastic			1.30		0.28	1.30	1.45	0.93	63.8	7
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Total			4.40		0.58	4.40	4.32	2.48	57.4	6
N _{tot}	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		0.24	28.8	20	29.5	29.0	28.9	2.1	7.3	12
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		0.20	29.8	20	30.4	29.9	29.8	2.0	6.6	12
Organic matter	% m/m DM	BioCom1		0.98	52.8	10	55.4	52.5	52.8	1.7	3.3	10
	% m/m DM	BioCom2		1.66	54.2	10	58.7	53.1	54.2	2.7	5.1	11

Participant 8													
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2*s _{pt} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}	
pH		BioCom1		0.74	8.04	3.7	8.15	8.05	8.03	0.11	1.4	14	
		BioCom2		1.20	7.72	3.9	7.90	7.70	7.71	0.12	1.5	14	
TOC	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		0.17	284	15	288	282	284	22	7.6	10	
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		-0.32	285	15	278	282	285	19	6.5	10	

Participant 9													
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2*s _{pt} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}	
Bulk density	g/l	BioCom1		0.18	549	10	554	540	549	24	4.4	11	
	g/l	BioCom2		0.46	522	10	534	515	522	22	4.3	11	
Conductivity 25	mS/m	BioCom1		-1.50	331	20	282	331	339	37	10.8	12	
	mS/m	BioCom2		0.13	357	15	361	354	357	16	4.5	11	
Dry matter, DM	% by mass	BioCom1		0.03	48.6	6	48.7	48.6	48.6	0.6	1.2	14	
	% by mass	BioCom2		-0.39	51.4	6	50.8	51.1	51.4	0.9	1.8	14	
Impurities, IMP	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Glass			1.38		<1	1.38	1.54	1.06	69.1	5	
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Metal			0.17		<1.0	0.17	0.32	0.38	120.7	5	
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Plastic			1.90		1.90	1.90	1.96	1.49	75.8	7	
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Total			2.80		1.90	2.80	3.08	2.16	70.2	6	
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Glass			2.19		2.20	2.19	2.75	1.93	70.2	6	
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Metal			0.46		<1	0.46	0.57	0.59	103.7	4	
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Plastic			1.30		1.80	1.30	1.45	0.93	63.8	7	
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Total			4.40		4.00	4.40	4.32	2.48	57.4	6	
N _{tot}	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		0.33	28.8	20	29.8	29.0	28.9	2.1	7.3	12	
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		0.22	29.8	20	30.5	29.9	29.8	2.0	6.6	12	
Organic matter	% m/m DM	BioCom1		-0.45	52.8	10	51.6	52.5	52.8	1.7	3.3	10	
	% m/m DM	BioCom2		-0.41	54.2	10	53.1	53.1	54.2	2.7	5.1	11	
pH		BioCom1		0.07	8.04	3.7	8.05	8.05	8.03	0.11	1.4	14	
		BioCom2		-1.46	7.72	3.9	7.50	7.70	7.71	0.12	1.5	14	
Stability	mmol O2/kg OM/h	BioCom1			3.69		2.80	3.69	5.84	5.54	94.9	4	
	mmol O2/kg OM/h	BioCom2			2.09		2.09	2.09	2.11	0.49	23.2	3	
TOC	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		-0.88	284	15	265	282	284	22	7.6	10	
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		-0.31	285	15	278	282	285	19	6.5	10	

Participant 10													
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2*s _{pt} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}	
Dry matter, DM	% by mass	BioCom1		-0.60	48.6	6	47.7	48.6	48.6	0.6	1.2	14	
	% by mass	BioCom2		-0.81	51.4	6	50.2	51.1	51.4	0.9	1.8	14	
N _{tot}	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		-0.46	28.8	20	27.5	29.0	28.9	2.1	7.3	12	
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		-0.21	29.8	20	29.2	29.9	29.8	2.0	6.6	12	
Organic matter	% m/m DM	BioCom1		0.77	52.8	10	54.8	52.5	52.8	1.7	3.3	10	
	% m/m DM	BioCom2		0.26	54.2	10	54.9	53.1	54.2	2.7	5.1	11	
pH		BioCom1		-0.76	8.04	3.7	7.93	8.05	8.03	0.11	1.4	14	
		BioCom2		-1.01	7.72	3.9	7.57	7.70	7.71	0.12	1.5	14	

Participant 11												
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2*s _{pt} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}
Bulk density	g/l	BioCom1		-0.46	549	10	537	540	549	24	4.4	11
	g/l	BioCom2		-0.77	522	10	502	515	522	22	4.3	11
Conductivity 25	mS/m	BioCom1		-0.12	331	20	327	331	339	37	10.8	12
	mS/m	BioCom2		-0.11	357	15	354	354	357	16	4.5	11
Dry matter, DM	% by mass	BioCom1		0.24	48.6	6	49.0	48.6	48.6	0.6	1.2	14
	% by mass	BioCom2		0.00	51.4	6	51.4	51.1	51.4	0.9	1.8	14
Organic matter	% m/m DM	BioCom1		0.19	52.8	10	53.3	52.5	52.8	1.7	3.3	10
	% m/m DM	BioCom2		1.05	54.2	10	57.1	53.1	54.2	2.7	5.1	11
pH		BioCom1		-0.61	8.04	3.7	7.95	8.05	8.03	0.11	1.4	14
		BioCom2		-0.13	7.72	3.9	7.70	7.70	7.71	0.12	1.5	14

Participant 12												
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2*s _{pt} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}
Bulk density	g/l	BioCom1		-1.15	549	10	518	540	549	24	4.4	11
	g/l	BioCom2		-0.80	522	10	501	515	522	22	4.3	11
Conductivity 25	mS/m	BioCom1		-0.47	331	20	316	331	339	37	10.8	12
	mS/m	BioCom2		-0.17	357	15	353	354	357	16	4.5	11
Dry matter, DM	% by mass	BioCom1		-0.14	48.6	6	48.4	48.6	48.6	0.6	1.2	14
	% by mass	BioCom2		-0.19	51.4	6	51.1	51.1	51.4	0.9	1.8	14
Impurities, IMP	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Glass			1.38		0.92	1.38	1.54	1.06	69.1	5
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Metal			0.17		0.09	0.17	0.32	0.38	120.7	5
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Plastic			1.90		0.52	1.90	1.96	1.49	75.8	7
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Total			2.80		1.53	2.80	3.08	2.16	70.2	6
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Glass			2.19		4.41	2.19	2.75	1.93	70.2	6
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Metal			0.46		0.02	0.46	0.57	0.59	103.7	4
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Plastic			1.30		0.61	1.30	1.45	0.93	63.8	7
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Total			4.40		5.05	4.40	4.32	2.48	57.4	6
N _{tot}	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		-0.17	28.8	20	28.3	29.0	28.9	2.1	7.3	12
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		-0.15	29.8	20	29.4	29.9	29.8	2.0	6.6	12
Organic matter	% m/m DM	BioCom1		-0.21	52.8	10	52.3	52.5	52.8	1.7	3.3	10
	% m/m DM	BioCom2		-0.41	54.2	10	53.1	53.1	54.2	2.7	5.1	11
pH		BioCom1		-0.27	8.04	3.7	8.00	8.05	8.03	0.11	1.4	14
		BioCom2		-0.13	7.72	3.9	7.70	7.70	7.71	0.12	1.5	14
TOC	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		-1.13	284	15	260	282	284	22	7.6	10
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		-1.19	285	15	260	282	285	19	6.5	10

Participant 13												
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2*s _{pt} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}
Bulk density	g/l	BioCom1		5.14	549	10	690	540	549	24	4.4	11
	g/l	BioCom2		6.44	522	10	690	515	522	22	4.3	11
Conductivity 25	mS/m	BioCom1		1.74	331	20	389	331	339	37	10.8	12
	mS/m	BioCom2		3.57	357	15	453	354	357	16	4.5	11
Dry matter, DM	% by mass	BioCom1		0.41	48.6	6	49.2	48.6	48.6	0.6	1.2	14
	% by mass	BioCom2		-0.26	51.4	6	51.0	51.1	51.4	0.9	1.8	14
Impurities, IMP	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Glass			1.38		<1.0	1.38	1.54	1.06	69.1	5
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Metal			0.17		<1.0	0.17	0.32	0.38	120.7	5
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Plastic			1.90		4.60	1.90	1.96	1.49	75.8	7
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Total			2.80		15.00	2.80	3.08	2.16	70.2	6
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Glass			2.19		<1.0	2.19	2.75	1.93	70.2	6
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Metal			0.46		<1.0	0.46	0.57	0.59	103.7	4
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Plastic			1.30		3.10	1.30	1.45	0.93	63.8	7
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Total			4.40		27.60	4.40	4.32	2.48	57.4	6
N _{tot}	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		0.47	28.8	20	30.2	29.0	28.9	2.1	7.3	12
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		0.49	29.8	20	31.3	29.9	29.8	2.0	6.6	12
Organic matter	% m/m DM	BioCom1		-0.47	52.8	10	51.6	52.5	52.8	1.7	3.3	10
	% m/m DM	BioCom2		-0.52	54.2	10	52.8	53.1	54.2	2.7	5.1	11
pH		BioCom1		0.07	8.04	3.7	8.05	8.05	8.03	0.11	1.4	14
		BioCom2		-0.13	7.72	3.9	7.70	7.70	7.71	0.12	1.5	14
TOC	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		0.74	284	15	300	282	284	22	7.6	10
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		1.03	285	15	307	282	285	19	6.5	10

Participant 14												
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2*s _{pt} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}
Bulk density	g/l	BioCom1		-1.05	549	10	520	540	549	24	4.4	11
	g/l	BioCom2		-1.00	522	10	496	515	522	22	4.3	11
Conductivity 25	mS/m	BioCom1		-0.39	331	20	318	331	339	37	10.8	12
	mS/m	BioCom2		-0.37	357	15	347	354	357	16	4.5	11
Dry matter, DM	% by mass	BioCom1		0.51	48.6	6	49.4	48.6	48.6	0.6	1.2	14
	% by mass	BioCom2		0.91	51.4	6	52.8	51.1	51.4	0.9	1.8	14
N _{tot}	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		1.65	28.8	20	33.6	29.0	28.9	2.1	7.3	12
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		1.04	29.8	20	32.9	29.9	29.8	2.0	6.6	12
Organic matter	% m/m DM	BioCom1		-1.19	52.8	10	49.7	52.5	52.8	1.7	3.3	10
	% m/m DM	BioCom2		-1.81	54.2	10	49.3	53.1	54.2	2.7	5.1	11
pH		BioCom1		0.57	8.04	3.7	8.13	8.05	8.03	0.11	1.4	14
		BioCom2		0.60	7.72	3.9	7.81	7.70	7.71	0.12	1.5	14
TOC	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		-0.07	284	15	283	282	284	22	7.6	10
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		0.00	285	15	285	282	285	19	6.5	10

Participant 15												
Measurand	Unit	Sample		z score	Assigned value	2*s _{ref} %	Participant's result	Md	Mean	s	s %	n _{stat}
Bulk density	g/l	BioCom1		-0.40	549	10	538	540	549	24	4.4	11
	g/l	BioCom2		-0.41	522	10	511	515	522	22	4.3	11
Conductivity 25	mS/m	BioCom1		-0.44	331	20	316	331	339	37	10.8	12
	mS/m	BioCom2		-0.21	357	15	352	354	357	16	4.5	11
Dry matter, DM	% by mass	BioCom1		0.00	48.6	6	48.6	48.6	48.6	0.6	1.2	14
	% by mass	BioCom2		-0.04	51.4	6	51.3	51.1	51.4	0.9	1.8	14
Impurities, IMP	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Glass			1.38		1.38	1.38	1.54	1.06	69.1	5
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Metal			0.17		0.32	0.17	0.32	0.38	120.7	5
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Plastic			1.90		1.99	1.90	1.96	1.49	75.8	7
	g/kg DM	BioCom1_Total			2.80		3.70	2.80	3.08	2.16	70.2	6
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Glass			2.19		2.17	2.19	2.75	1.93	70.2	6
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Metal			0.46		0.72	0.46	0.57	0.59	103.7	4
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Plastic			1.30		1.87	1.30	1.45	0.93	63.8	7
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_Total			4.40		4.80	4.40	4.32	2.48	57.4	6
N _{tot}	g/kg DM	BioCom1_DG		-0.85	28.8	20	26.4	29.0	28.9	2.1	7.3	12
	g/kg DM	BioCom2_DG		-1.02	29.8	20	26.8	29.9	29.8	2.0	6.6	12
Organic matter	% m/m DM	BioCom1		-0.08	52.8	10	52.6	52.5	52.8	1.7	3.3	10
	% m/m DM	BioCom2		0.70	54.2	10	56.1	53.1	54.2	2.7	5.1	11
pH		BioCom1		0.67	8.04	3.7	8.14	8.05	8.03	0.11	1.4	14
		BioCom2		0.80	7.72	3.9	7.84	7.70	7.71	0.12	1.5	14

Appendix 8. Results of participants and their uncertainties

The dashed lines in figures describe the standard deviation for the proficiency assessment, red solid line shows the assigned value, shaded area describes the expanded uncertainty of the assigned value, and arrow describes the value outside the scale.

Measurand Dry matter, DM Sample BioCom2

Measurand Impurities, IMP Sample BioCom1_Glass

Measurand Impurities, IMP Sample BioCom1_Metal

Measurand Impurities, IMP Sample BioCom1_Plastic

Measurand Impurities, IMP Sample BioCom1_Total

Measurand Impurities, IMP Sample BioCom2_Glass

Measurand Impurities, IMP Sample BioCom2_Metal

Measurand Impurities, IMP Sample BioCom2_Plastic

Measurand Impurities, IMP Sample BioCom2_Total

Measurand Organic matter Sample BioCom2

Measurand pH Sample BioCom1

Measurand pH Sample BioCom2

Measurand Stability Sample BioCom1

Measurand Stability Sample BioCom2

Measurand TOC Sample BioCom1_DG

Appendix 9. Summary of the z scores

Measurand	Sample	1	2	3	4	5	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	%
Bulk density	BioCom1	<i>Q</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	.	<i>S</i>	S	<i>U</i>	<i>S</i>	S	84.6
	BioCom2	<i>U</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	.	<i>S</i>	S	<i>U</i>	<i>S</i>	S	84.6
Conductivity 25	BioCom1	<i>Q</i>	<i>u</i>	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	.	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	84.6
	BioCom2	<i>S</i>	<i>u</i>	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	.	<i>S</i>	S	<i>U</i>	<i>S</i>	S	84.6
Dry matter, DM	BioCom1	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	S	S	S	<i>S</i>	S	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	100
	BioCom2	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	S	S	S	<i>S</i>	S	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	100
N _{tot}	BioCom1_DG	.	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	.	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	100
	BioCom2_DG	.	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	.	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	100
Organic matter	BioCom1	.	<i>u</i>	<i>u</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>u</i>	S	S	<i>S</i>	S	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	76.9
	BioCom2	.	<i>u</i>	<i>u</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	S	<i>S</i>	S	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	84.6
pH	BioCom1	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	100
	BioCom2	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	100
TOC	BioCom1_DG	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	.	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	.	.	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	.	100
	BioCom2_DG	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	.	<i>S</i>	S	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	.	.	<i>S</i>	<i>S</i>	S	.	100
%		70	71	86	100	100	93	100	100	100	100	100	79	100	100	
accredited		2			6	2	6	4	8		4	10		4	6	

S - satisfactory ($-2.0 \leq z \leq 2.0$), Q - questionable ($2.0 < z < 3.0$), q - questionable ($-3.0 < z < -2.0$),

U - unsatisfactory ($z \geq 3.0$), and u - unsatisfactory ($z \leq -3.0$), respectively

bold - accredited, italics - non-accredited

% - percentage of satisfactory results

Satisfactory results, in total %: 93 in accredited %: 100 in non-accredited %: 90

Appendix 10. z scores in ascending order

Measurand Bulk density Sample BioCom1

Measurand Bulk density Sample BioCom2

Measurand Conductivity 25 Sample BioCom1

Measurand Conductivity 25 Sample BioCom2

Measurand Dry matter, DM Sample BioCom1

Measurand Dry matter, DM Sample BioCom2

Measurand N_{tot} Sample BioCom1_DG

Measurand N_{tot} Sample BioCom2_DG

Measurand Organic matter Sample BioCom1

Measurand Organic matter Sample BioCom2

Measurand pH Sample BioCom1

Measurand pH Sample BioCom2

Measurand TOC Sample BioCom1_DG

Measurand TOC Sample BioCom2_DG

Appendix 11. Answers to the background survey on analytical methods

Participant	Measurand	1	2	3	4, 15	5	7	8	9	10	12	13
Which of the analyses are accredited for compost/soil improvers in your laboratory?	pH	No	No	No	Yes	No	-	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
	Electrical conductivity (EC)	No	No	No	Yes	No	-	No	No	-	Yes	No
	Bulk density (BD)	No	No	No	Yes	No	-	No	No	-	Yes	No
	Dry matter (DM)	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
	TOC	Yes	No	No	-	No	Yes	No	No	-	No	No
	N _{tot}	No	No	No		No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No
	Impurities (IMP)	No	No	No	-	-	-	No	No	-	Yes	No
	Stability (OUR)	No	No	No	-	-	-	No	No	-	-	No
	Organic matter (OM)	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	-	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No

1. pH / Participant	1	2	3	4,15	5	6	7	8	9	10	12	13
Do you use standard method? a. Yes	-	EN 13037	EN 13037	EN 13037	EN 13037	-	EN 13037	-	-	-	EN 13037; 2012-01	EN13037
b. No, describe method (e.g. modified standard method or in-house method).	In house based on EN 13037	-	-	-	-	-	-	pH determination at room temperature with combined electrode	In-house method based on UNE-EN 13037	We use modified standard 13037. Extraction ratio 1+5 (by mass), shaken and measured. Two parallel samples. The pH meter was calibrated with standard buffer solutions of pH 4, 7, and 10.	-	-
What solution and sample-to-liquid ratio were used?	1: 5 (v/v)	1:5	1:5	1:5	1:5	1:5 ¹⁾	-	Water extract 1/15 (W/V)	1:5 (w/v) ratio	reverse osmosis water, sample-to-liquid ratio 1:5 (by mass)	H ₂ O, 1+5	60/300 (ml sample to ml liquid)

¹⁾ Deionized water (MQ) in a ratio of 1:5. 1) 60 ml sample + 300 ml water. The sample was weighed for water extraction in a weight (g) corresponding to 60 ml of sample volume using the bulk density (g/l) determined in the calculation

2. EC / Participant	1	2	3	4, 15	5	7	8	9	12	13
Do you use standard method? a. Yes	-	-	EN 13038	EN 13038	EN 13038	EN 13038	EN 13038	-	EN 13038; 2012-01	EN13038
b. No, describe method (e.g. modified standard method or in-house method).	In-house method based on EN 13038	In-house method based on EN 13038	-	-	-	-	But with internal method of determination of bulk density	In-house method based on EN 13038	-	-
What solution and sample-to-liquid ratio were used?	1:5 (v/v)	1:5	1:5	1:5	1:5	1:5 ¹⁾	Water extract 60/300 (V/V)	1:5 (v/v) ratio	H ₂ O, 1+5	60/300 (ml sample to ml liquid)

¹⁾ Deionized water (MQ) in a ratio of 1:5. 1) 60 ml sample + 300 ml water. The sample was weighed for water extraction in a weight (g) corresponding to 60 ml of sample volume using the bulk density (g/l) determined in the calculation

3. BD / Participant	1	2	3	4, 15	5	7	8	9	12	13
Do you use standard method? a. Yes	-	-	EN 13040-1	EN 13040	EN 13040	EN 13040	-	-	EN 13040; 2008-01	EN 13040-1
b. No, describe method (e.g. modified standard method or in-house method).	In-house method based on EN13040-1	In-house method based on EN 13040-1	-	-	-	-	Manually compacted density - no special equipment	In-house method based on UNE-EN 13040:2008	-	-
How long was the weight applied to the sample?	3 minutes	180 s	3 minutes	3 minutes	3 minutes	3 min (180 s) based on EN 13040	No weight used	-	180 s +/- 10 s	-

4. DM / Participant	1	2	3	4, 15	5	7	8	9	10	12	13
Do you use standard method? a. Yes	EN 15934	-	EN13040-1	EN 13040	-	EN 13040	-	-	EN 13039	EN 13040; 2008-01	EN 13040-1
b. No, describe method (e.g. modified standard method or in-house method).	-	In-house method based on EN 13040-1	-	-	In-house method (Thermo gravimetric analyser)	-	Drying at 103°C for 40 hours minimum	In-house method	-	-	-
5. Organic matter											
Do you use standard method? a. Yes	-	-	EN 13039	EN 13039	-	EN 13039			EN 13039	EN 13039; 2012-01	EN 13039
b. No, describe method (e.g. modified standard method or in-house method).	-	In-house method based on EN 13040-1	-	-	In-house method (Thermo gravimetric analyser)	-	Calcination at 550°C for 3 hours minimum	In-house method based on EN 15935	-	-	-

6. TOC / Participant	1	2	3	5	7	8	9	12
Do you use standard method? a. Yes	EN 15936	-	-	-	EN 15936, EN 13137 withdrawn	-	-	EN 15936; 2012-11
b. No, describe method (e.g. modified standard method or in-house method).	-	Internal method	In house combustion-based approach (Dumas): acidification combustion + detection (TC-detector)	In-house method (Dumas)	-	Dumas	In-house method	-

7. N _{tot} / Participant	2	3	4, 15	5	7	8	9	10	12	13
Do you use standard method? a. Yes	-	EN 13654-1	-	EN 13654-2	5505:1998, ISO 11261, EN 16169 modified Kjeldahl	EN 13654-2	-	-	EN 16168; 2012-11	CEN/TS 17776
b. No, describe method (e.g. modified standard method or in-house method).	Internal method	-	In-house method: 1g dry sample is weighed to Kjeldahl tube, sulphuric acid (1+1) and NiAl alloy 1,7g inserted. Heated 185 C 0,5h and then 390 C 1h.	-	-	-	In-house method based on UNE-EN 13654-2	The nitrogen content of the samples was determined with an in-house Kjeldahl method according to the Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC) method 2001.11, EN ISO 20483:2013 and EN ISO 5983-2.	-	-

8. Impurities / Participants	3	8	9	12	13
Do you use standard method? a. Yes	EN 16202	-	-	National standards	EN 16202
b. No, describe method.	-	Treatment of a minimum of 100g of raw product, previously homogenized, with bleach for 65 hours, followed by manual washing and sorting.	In-house method	-	-
What was the sample portion size? (e.g. 1 kg, 1 l, other)	1 kg	100 g	50-60 g	1000 ml	250 g
How were metals separated?	Manually + magnet	Manually	Manually	manually + check with magnet	manually
Were there any materials that did not fit into the three impurity categories or were difficult to identify? Please describe.	Stones > 2 mm	No	There were stones in the sample	According to the method we distinguish between hard plastics and plastic films, these were combined in the results for this trial // compounds (e.g. cable with plastic and metal) and other materials (e.g. leather, some rubber or fleece materials, ceramics) are considered as others, in this trial we found fleece and yarn)	

9. Stability (OUR) / Participant	3	6	8	9
Do you use standard method? a. Yes	EN16087-1	EN 16087-1 (2020)	-	-
b. No, describe method	-	-	Not done	In-house method based on EN 16087-1:2020
What incubation temperature was used?	20 °C	30°C	-	30°C
What amount of organic matter was included in the sample portion?	sample portion 5g (OM 27%)	We repeated the test (for both samples) twice. See note. ²⁾	-	5 g
How long was the suspension stirred before measurement started?	4 hours	0 h	-	4 h
How were the results calculated? For example, was the linear phase determined visually or using mathematical models?	Visually	Visually	-	Visual

²⁾ In the first test, we set the test with 2gSV as the standard. However, the standard states that "if it appears during the test that the pressure drop during the first three days is not higher than 2kPa, then the amount of organic matter should be increased but with maximum of 20g dry matter". So, we restarted the test with 20 g dry matter. For a future interlaboratory test, I think it would be useful to analyse less stable matrices. The results of the OUR tests on the BioCom1 and BioCom2 samples are very close to the instrument's detection limits.

10. Does your laboratory face any specific challenges in analysing any of the parameters listed above?

Participant	Answer
1	None on the parameters that we do analyse.
3	No specific comments.
4	No
7	The determination of the loss on ignition resulted in an unusual deviation of parallel results. After the results were sent, the loss on ignition analysis was repeated and a smaller deviation of results was obtained that met our own requirements.
8	Several impurity tests were conducted with a lack of repeatability.
9	No
10	Measuring total nitrogen from dried sample using wet combustion and Kjeldahl apparatus is somewhat challenging due to small actual sample amount.
12	No
13	No

Appendix 12. Results grouped according to the methods

The explanations for the figures are described in Appendix 9. The results are shown in ascending order.

Measurand Conductivity 25 Sample BioCom1

Measurand Conductivity 25 Sample BioCom2

Measurand Dry matter, DM Sample BioCom1

Measurand Impurities, IMP Sample BioCom1_Plastic

Measurand Impurities, IMP Sample BioCom1_Total

Measurand Impurities, IMP Sample BioCom2_Glass

Measurand Impurities, IMP Sample BioCom2_Metal

Measurand Impurities, IMP Sample BioCom2_Plastic

Measurand Impurities, IMP Sample BioCom2_Total

Measurand Organic matter Sample BioCom2

Measurand pH Sample BioCom 1

Measurand pH Sample BioCom2

Measurand Stability Sample BioCom1

Measurand Stability Sample BioCom2

Measurand TOC Sample BioCom1_DG

Appendix 13. Examples of measurement uncertainties reported by the participants

In figures, the presented expanded measurement uncertainties are grouped according to the method of evaluation at 95 % confidence level ($k=2$). The expanded uncertainties were evaluated mainly by using the internal quality control (IQC) data. The procedures used in figures below are distinguished e.g. between using or not using the MUKIT software for uncertainty evaluation [9, 10].

Measurand Dry matter, DM Sample BioCom1

Measurand N_{tot} Sample BioCom2_DG

Measurand Organic matter Sample BioCom2

Interlaboratory comparison 12/2025

Analyses of biowaste compost quality parameters

Suomen ympäristökeskus
Finlands miljöcentral
Finnish Environment Institute

ISBN 978-952-11-5831-5 (PDF)
ISSN 1796-1726 (online)

We build hope through research.